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Assessment of Factors Influencing Career Choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria

SANNI, Rabiat

rabiat.sanni@gmail.com
08036064547, 08022226462

Students Affairs Division, Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated the Assessment of factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja local government area of Kogi. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 7225(4648 males and 2545 female) senior secondary school students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Lokoja local government area of Kogi State. 500 (297 male and 203 female) constitute the sample size of the study selected using multistage sampling techniques. A research instrument titled “Influences on Career Choice Questionnaire (ICCQ)” was used for data collection. to ensure the validity of the instrument, face and content was ensured by expert while the reliability of the instrument was done using split-half formula with a reliability coefficient of 0.7. One research question and two research hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The data collected were analyzed using frequency count, mean, percentage and standard deviation to answer the research question and t-test analysis for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that peers, family, school, gender and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The study concluded that peers and family are the major factors that can influence the career choice of secondary school students. The study recommends that there is a need to review the career guidance curriculum to consider factors that influence students’ choices of careers.

Keyword: career choice, peers, family and secondary school.

Introduction

With a population of over 200 million, Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa. However, choosing appropriate career paths for its fast expanding population presents serious challenges (Adeyanju, Mogaji, Olusola, & Oyinlola, 2020). An individual need to be aware of his talents and shortcomings in order to have a sensible and practical career. Comprehending them will enable him to accomplish his objective. His inspiration will come from his goal (Korkmaz & Kirdok, 2020).

Making a career choice is a crucial decision that students make as they advance through secondary school. While some students from enriched environments begin this decision-making process early, for other students who struggled to come to grips with who they were and what they wanted to become in the future, the process begins much later. Adolescents' professional decisions are, of course, based on the knowledge at their disposal. In fact, a variety of internal and external factors may interact to influence students' career selections in a timely or inefficient manner (Haruna, 2016).

Owusu, Owusu, Fiorgbor, and Kumah, (2020), claimed that Career refers to a person's professional course or an occupation which he/she has to follow over a number of years, affording him/her the opportunity for progress as well as serving as his principal means of earning a living and in which he/she is generally recognised to have become fairly an expert in, through experience. Career is a life time pursuit for success Eremie & Okwulehie (2019).

According to Oduh, Agbola and Eibhalemen (2020), “Making a decision concerning the selection of suitable career or occupation is one significant problem facing senior secondary school students and young adolescents in general. This may be due to lack of information, understanding, orientation, awareness, training and opportunities about activities in different careers or vocations”. This brings up the topic of choosing a career. The process by which a person decides, at a given moment, to pursue a particular profession or vocation after carefully weighing all of his options is referred to as career choice.

Choosing a career is one of the most important and challenging decisions a person will ever have to make because it is a developmental process that affects a person for the majority of their life. This decision should be made after considering the ramifications or requirements of entering the field of career. This is why a student needs to be systematically furnished with relevant career information to enable him/her make a realistic career decision (Ahmad, et. al., 2019).

The complexities noted above about career choice have compelled many young people to seek assistance from members of the age group in an attempt to resolve the seeming impasse. This refers to the influence a peer group exerts on an individual that encourages the individual to change his or her attitude, values or behaviour to conform to such a group (Kirk in Oduh, Agbola

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& Eibhalemen2020). Also, apart from the influence exerted by parents, some students may want to identify with their friends in the class. Hence, they choose subject combinations which would lead to certain careers simply because a friend belongs to that particular group.

Obot, amalu, apebende and ogodo (2020) found out in their study of Peer group and career aspiration of secondary school students in Northern Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria that, peer group significantly influences students' career aspiration. A further consideration of their results show that, for all careers, average level of peer influence, has more students, followed by low level with the lowest number of the students falling under high influence. Also, the study conducted by Nwoka, Okafor, & Nnubia (2022) revealed that parental values and family background influence students' career choice to a great extent.

owusu, owusu, fiorgbor and atakora (2021) in their research on Career Aspiration of Students: The Influence of Peers, Teachers and Parents found out that what they want to be in future is influenced by their friends, their choices of courses are influenced by their friends and that the manner in which they learn is as a result of how their friends learned. This simply implied that overall the respondents agreed to most of the statements showing that peers had a great influence on the career aspirations of students. The study also revealed that parents had interest in the careers of their children and that their children do not take career decisions without their approval.

Yunusa, Jaafar, Ismail and Othman (2022), in their research on A Study on the Relationship between Family Peer Group Media and Career Decision Making among Undergraduates in Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that family (parents) has a significant relationship with career decision making. The study also found that peer groups have no significant link with career decision-making, of the students as seen by the result of the findings.

Ajayi, Moosa, and Aloka, (2022), investigate the Influence of selected social factors on career decision making of grade 12 learners in township secondary schools in South Africa. The result of the study revealed that, there was a strong link between teacher influence and career decision-making, followed by the link between career information services and career decision-making, but peer influence had the weakest link with career decision-making. The influence of older siblings on students in Grade 12 had a considerable direct association with professional decision-making.

Chukwu, Ogidi, Akaneme, & Ilechukwu, (2022) in their study of factors influencing career choice among secondary school student in Aba North of Abia State found out The grand mean rating of the influence regarding peer group on students' choice of career is 2.9 and a standard deviation score of 0.40, which is higher than the benchmark of 2.5. By implication, students are influenced by their peers regarding career choice as revealed in item 20 with the mean score of 3.4. Peers' suggestions count in career choice. The grand mean rating with regards to the influence of parents on the student's career choice is 3.1 and the standard deviation of 0.58, which is higher than the benchmark of 2.5. By implication students generally submit to the influence of their parents regarding career choice.

From the empirical review within the reach of the researcher, it was observed that not much work had been carried out on peers and family influence on career choice, especially within Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. This is the gap this study filled.

Statement of The Research problem

In today's world, selecting a career is often a challenge for students. For this reason, it is not unusual for students to enter careers that are not entirely suited to their abilities. On the other hand, peer group and parental background frequently play a major role in influencing a student's job decision. Due to peculiarities in their own lives, parents frequently push their children into pursuing family careers and other professions even though they lack the necessary skills. In the end, what typically happens is job discontent, poor performance, if not outright malfunction, frustration, and inefficiency, all of which contribute to a national economic catastrophe over time. Hence the need for the assessment of factors influencing career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja local government area of Kogi State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate

1. The influence of family factor on career choice Among Senior Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. The influence of peer factor on career choice Among Senior Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Research Question

1. What are the factors that influences choice of career among senior secondary school students in Lokoja Government Area of Kogi State?

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Research Hypothesis

- i. There is no significant difference between Family influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.
- ii. There is no significant difference between peer influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study consists of all Government senior secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria which is 7225 (4648 males and 2545 females) students (Source: Kogi State Science, Technical Education and Teaching Service Commission). The sample for the study consists of 500 (297 males and females 203) students selected from all the government owned secondary school in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling techniques. The first state was proportional sampling techniques for the respondent based on the number of student per school and the second stage is a simple random techniques for the respondents. The researcher instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher titled Influences on Career Choice Questionnaire (ICCQ).

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument, face and content validities were ensured by experts while the reliability of the instrument was established by administering the instrument on 40 secondary school students Government Day secondary school Adankolo, Lokoja. Data collected were analysed using split-half Formula with a reliability coefficient of 0.7 hence the instrument was adjudged to be reliable for the study. The data obtained from the instrument was analyse using the descriptive analysis of frequency count, mean, percentage and standard deviation were used to answer research question raised for the study. The hypotheses generated were subjected to inferential statistics of t-test analysis and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the factors that influences choice of career among secondary school students in Lokoja Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 1: factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State

Influencing factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Rank
Peers	310 (62%)	100 (20%)	40 (8%)	50 (10%)	3.34	1 st
Family	150 (30%)	250 (50%)	30 (6%)	70 (14%)	2.96	2 nd
School	150 (30%)	130 (26%)	120 (24%)	100 (20%)	2.66	3 rd
Role Model	80(16%)	210 (42%)	100 (20%)	110 (22%)	2.52	4 th
Gender	70 (14%)	20 (4%)	100 (20%)	310 (62%)	1.70	5 th

Table 1 presents the factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The result shows that, with a cutoff mean of 2.50 for the rating scale, all the items had a mean scores above the cutoff except gender. This implies that peers, family, school and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. The factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State are shown in Figure I.

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Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between family influence and choice of career choice Among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to family influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State, were computed and subjected to Statistical analysis involving t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test showing the difference between family influence and choice of career among secondary school students in Lokoja Local government Area of Kogi State.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t_{cal}	t_{table}
Family factor	500	15.50	1.25			
				499	169.750*	1.960
Career Choice	500	6.76	0.56			

* $p < 0.05$

Table 2 shows that $t_{cal}(169.750)$ is greater than $t_{table}(1.960)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between family influence and choice of career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between Peers influence and choice of career Among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to peers' influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: t-test showing the influence of peers on career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

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<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>t_{cal}</i>	<i>t_{table}</i>
Peers	500	15.50	1.25			
				119	128.340*	1.960
Career Choice	500	6.85	0.94			

* $p < 0.05$

Table 3 reveals that t_{cal} (128.340) is greater than t_{table} (1.960) at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between peer influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Discussion

The result shows that peers, family, school and role model are factors that influence career choice among secondary school students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State while gender is least in terms of influence on the career choice of secondary school students. The finding agreed with Ajayi, Moosa, and Aloka, (2022) with as they found out that there was a strong link between teacher influence and career decision-making, followed by the link between career information services and career decision-making, but peer influence had the weakest link with career decision-making.

The finding of the study shows that there is significant difference between family influence and career choice among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. Most of the students were viewed as coming to school with predetermined careers which may be a result of interacting with the immediate environment and their parents' help in choosing their careers. This study is in line with Owusu, Owusu, Fiorgbor and Atakora (2021) who revealed that parents had interest in the careers of their children and that their children do not take career decisions without their approval. This therefore means that family members play a significant role in the choice of career of the young people. In this study, parental advice played a role in influencing career among sponsored students. Following closely were uncle's and auntie's advice on career choice.

The finding of the study shows that there is a significant difference between the peers' influence and choice of career among Secondary School Students in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. As students interact with peers and friends, they share important information on career choices. Career guidance teachers were in agreement with student participants as they reinforced that career advice from friends was influential to students' choices of careers. The finding agrees Obot, Amalu, Apebende and Ogodo (2020) who revealed that peer group significantly influences students' career aspiration. A further consideration of their results show that, for all careers, average level of peer influence, has more students, followed by low level with the lowest number of the students falling under high influence. The results of this study concur with this since mentorship of the respondents by their friends, friend's approval of career choice and friend's advice were proved to have a great influence on their choice of career.

Conclusions

The essence of the study was to establish factors that influence the choice of career among students in lokoja local government area of kogi state. As reflected by the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the family has a significant role in influencing students' career choices. The study further concluded that peers have a significant role in students' choices of careers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study on factors influencing the career choices of students, the following recommendations are made:

- I. There is a need to review the career guidance curriculum to consider factors that influence students' choices of careers.
- II. There should be a paradigm shift from the career guidance teacher as the sole provider of career guidance in schools.
- III. It is also recommended that clear policy on who should teach career guidance and the actual provision of career guidance in schools be put in place.

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